
Quantity vs. Quality? Unpacking the Evolution and Evaluation of Management Research in India

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ABSTRACT

Over the last two decades, management education and research in India have been accompanied by an intensification of performance-based evaluation systems. These systems increasingly prioritise publication counts, citation-based metrics, and journal rankings. Although these mechanisms were introduced to boost global visibility and research productivity, they have also created a persistent strain between research quantity and research quality. This paper examines this strain by positioning the evolution of management research in India within the broader context of global, metrics-driven academic governance.

Drawing on institutional theory, principal-agent theory, and the literature on academic capitalism and knowledge production systems, the paper examines how regulatory mandates from regulators such as the University Grants Commission, together with the globalisation of journal rankings and citation metrics, have reshaped incentive structures for scholars and institutions. The paper argues that an excessive dependence on publication counts and journal-based proxies for quality puts undue pressure on faculty members to focus on short-termism, opportunistic publishing behaviour, and methodological conformity. This is resulting in unintended and undesirable outcomes, such as a decline in sustained, theory-building research, proliferation of lower-quality publications, and ethical misconduct.

Simultaneously, the paper challenges the binary framing of quantity versus quality in research evaluation. Excellence in research is inherently multidimensional and context-dependent, particularly in the context of academic systems such as India. The paper advocates for an integrated evaluation framework that assesses research across four dimensions: inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes. It also recognises differentiated expectations across career stages and institutional types, while integrating global standards with contextual and local relevance.

The paper contributes to the literature by reconceptualising research quality beyond narrow bibliometric indicators and by offering policy-relevant recommendations for regulators, institutions, and individual scholars. It concludes by outlining directions for future empirical research on research evaluation.

KEYWORDS: Evaluation Frameworks, Institutional Theory, Management Research, Publish-Or-Perish, Research Evaluation, Research Quantity And Quality.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Management research plays a vital role in shaping policy discourse, managerial practice, and organisational effectiveness. Evaluation of management research has been increasingly subjugated by quantitative performance metrics, such as citation-based indicators and journal rankings. These developments have substantially transformed academic incentives and research behaviour. In this backdrop, this section presents the context, statement of the problem, research issues, scope, and contributions of the study by situating the quantity-quality dilemma within the growing landscape of management research in India.

1.1 Background and Context

The higher education system in India has undergone phenomenal growth over the last two decades. The number of universities, deemed-to-be-universities, colleges, autonomous colleges, management institutions (M-schools), etc., has increased significantly and rapidly. Furthermore, one can find a sharp rise in doctoral enrolments and faculty positions (Bornmann, 2017; Borthakur et al., 2024). Once concentrated in a very few elite institutions, management education and research have evolved into a large and heterogeneous set of institutions consisting of government universities (both central and state), private institutions, and specialised M-schools (Altbach, 2006; Khatri et al., 2012). This expansion has been accompanied by rising expectations about global visibility, research productivity, and measurable academic performance.

Simultaneously, the globalisation of academic publication has primarily redesigned how management research is produced, disseminated, and evaluated. Notably, research productivity is increasingly measured through the publication of research papers indexed in international databases (Mathews et al., 2024). Journal ranking systems such as Scopus, the Australian Business Deans Council (ABDC) list, the Academic Journal Guide (AJG) of the Chartered Association of Business Schools (CABS), etc., have attained significant influence beyond their original national contexts (Serenko & Bontis, 2024). These lists now serve as global benchmarks for assessing the quality of research in management disciplines (Hazelkorn, 2015; Moed, 2017). These are the indicators of broader trends in global academia. Citation analysis, journal impact factors, and h-indices have become institutionalised mechanisms for evaluating research excellence (Gasparyan et al., 2018). Academic careers are also increasingly designed by a “publish-or-perish” culture (Smith et al., 2024), wherein the frequency of publication often serves as a proxy for scholarly merit (Elbanna & Child, 2023). At all career stages, researchers are under pressure to publish continuously to secure appointments, promotions, and professional legitimacy (Chiriboga, 2019). In this type of academic environment, citation-based indicators, publication counts, and journal rankings play a pivotal role in academic decision-making (Aguinis & Ramani, 2018; Hicks et al., 2015).

However, although these metrics provide both objectivity and comparability, their increasing dominance has also changed the incentive structures that govern academic work. Scholars (researchers/academics) may be encouraged/forced to maximise measurable outputs rather than to pursue long-term research agendas or deeper intellectual contributions (Rawat & Meena, 2014). This change raises questions about the nature and utility of knowledge being produced, and the future trajectory of management research in India.

1.2 Statement of the Problem: The Quantity-Quality Dilemma

The increasing dependence on metric-driven assessment and evaluation has intensified a longstanding issue between research quantity and research quality: (i) increasing publication numbers are often interpreted as indicators of scholarly productivity and institutional vitality, and (ii) apprehensions have grown to the effect that excessive emphasis on output counts may compromise theoretical originality (Figure 1), methodological rigor, and contextual relevance which are core parts of research quality (Alverson & Sandberg, 2013; Tourish, 2020).

Figure 1: The Quantity-Quality Dilemma in Management Research

This contradiction is well documented in the literature. As the number of publications has increased globally (Rawat & Meena, 2014), apprehensions about the declining quality of research have also intensified simultaneously (Verma & Sharma, 2024). Studies also revealed various unfavourable consequences of “publish-or-perish” pressures, such as questionable research practices (Downer et al., 2025), predatory publishing (Mertkan, Sefika et al., 2021), and other forms of academic misconduct (Poutoglidou et al., 2022). In the context of India, strong pressure to demonstrate research productivity through indexed publications has further incentivised

and intensified quantity-driven behaviour (Madhan et al., 2018). However, an increase in the number of publications does not necessarily translate into substantive contributions or greater intellectual impact (Rawat & Meena, 2014).

Institutional environment and incentive structures strengthen this dynamic. Performance-linked remuneration, promotion, and tenure are increasingly linked to publication counts in indexed journals (Wright & Sharma, 2013). From a principal-agent perspective, this results in a misalignment between system-level objectives and individual scholarly behaviour. Institutions and regulators seek increased research output and global visibility on the one hand, and individual scholars face immediate career pressures that may encourage and force tactical publishing strategies on the other, rather than sustained theory-building efforts (Smith et al., 2024). Practices such as salami slicing, duplicate publication, and strategic journal selection based on acceptance probabilities have become documented concerns (Thomas et al., 2024; Mingers & Willmott, 2012; Rawat & Meena, 2014). The central issue, therefore, lies not in the use of metrics per se, but in their uncritical application as proxies for research quality.

1.3 Research Issues/Questions and Analytical Focus

In light of the above, this paper addresses the following interrelated research issues/ questions:

- (a) How has management research in India evolved under increasingly metric-driven evaluation systems?
- (b) What are the institutional and incentive mechanisms that have driven this evolution?
- (c) What conceptual misalignments exist between “quantity” and “quality” in research evaluation, and why is binary framing problematic?
- (d) How adequate are existing evaluation frameworks in capturing meaningful scholarly contributions?
- (e) What are the alternative approaches that might better serve academic communities and society?

Instead of presenting an empirical analysis of publication patterns, this paper adopts a theory-driven and analytical focus. It examines the assumptions embedded in dominant research evaluation practices and examines how these assumptions interact with regulatory frameworks, institutional incentives, and global academic norms. In doing so, the study goes beyond descriptive critique and seeks to develop deeper conceptual insights into research evaluation in emerging academic systems.

1.4 Scope and Nature of the Study

This paper is conceptual in nature - not based on primary data collection, surveys, or bibliometric analysis. Instead, it utilises the established theoretical perspectives on knowledge production systems, institutional dynamics, principal-agent relationships, and academic capitalism to develop an integrated analytical framework. The emphasis is on management research in India, positioning within a comparative global context that highlights both convergence with, and divergence from, global trends.

The case of India is particularly enlightening due to the coexistence of strong regulatory oversight, rapid system expansion, and increasing exposure to global performance regimes. Although the analysis is context-specific, the arguments developed in this paper are relevant even to other emerging economies confronting similar pressures between global benchmarks and local scholarly priorities.

1.5 Contributions of the Paper

The paper makes three important contributions: (i) It advances theoretical discussion on research evaluation by critically evaluating the conceptual foundations of quantity and quality in management research, and by challenging their treatment as mutually exclusive objectives; (ii) It provides contextually founded insights into how global evaluation regimes interact with Indian institutional structures, scholarly traditions, and regulatory frameworks; and (iii) It proposes a balanced, multidimensional framework for research evaluation that moves beyond reductionist metrics while recognising legitimate concerns related to research productivity and institutional visibility.

1.6 Structure of the Paper

The remaining parts of the paper are presented as follows. Section 2 traces the evolution of management research in India across four phases, from early institution-building to contemporary metric-driven assessment. Section 3 conceptualises research quantity and quality, and analyses binary framing. Section 4 introduces the theoretical frameworks used to analyse research evaluation dynamics. Section 5 explores evaluation regimes and incentive structures in India. Section 6 proposes a comprehensive and integrated framework for balanced research evaluation. Section 7 presents policy implications and strategic recommendations. And finally, Section 8 concludes the paper and identifies directions for future research.

2. EVOLUTION OF MANAGEMENT RESEARCH IN INDIA

The evolution of management research in India replicates broader transformations in the country's higher education system, economic structure, and engagement with global knowledge networks. However, this evolution has not followed a linear trajectory. Instead, it has unfolded through a series of overlapping phases, each shaped by distinct institutional priorities, dominant research orientations, and evaluation norms. Comprehending these phases in the right perspective is necessary for contextualising the contemporary quantity-quality dilemma in Indian management scholarship. In light of this, a review of earlier studies is presented below chronologically (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Evolutionary Phases of Management Research in India

2.1 Early Phase (1960s–1990s): Institution-Building and Practice Orientation

In India, management education emerged in the post-independence period, driven by the need for skilled professionals to manage a growing and increasingly complex economy, particularly corporate enterprises. In this process, the establishment of premier M-schools such as the Indian Institutes of Management (IIMs) in the 1960s marked an important milestone (Kapur & Mehta, 2004; Altbach, 2006; Dhouchak & Kumar, 2023). Primarily/initially, these institutions were conceived as centres for high-quality management education and leadership development rather than as research-intensive universities.

However, during this phase, research activity was limited and largely subordinate to teaching, executive education, and consultancy. Faculty members in M-schools were deeply engaged in curriculum design and development, case writing, and practitioner-oriented problem solving. Research outputs emphasised on immediate managerial relevance, particularly in public sector undertakings (PSUs) and emerging private firms (Suresh, 2020). Scholarly dissemination took place through working papers, case repositories, practitioner-focused publications, and conference presentations, rather than through global peer-reviewed journals (Tourish, 2020). Furthermore, the valuation of scholarly work depended on peer recognition, teaching effectiveness, and contributions to institutional development instead of standardised quantitative metrics (Madhan et al., 2018). However, structural constraints also played a significant role. The absence of large-scale doctoral programs, limited access to foreign journals, and insufficient research funding for infrastructure constrained systematic theory-building initiatives. While this phase laid the institutional foundations of management education in India, it did not yet develop a strong publication-driven research culture aligned with global academic standards (Albach & Salmi, 2011).

2.2 Expansion Phase (1990s–2005): Massification and Doctoral Growth

The liberalisation-privatisation-globalisation (LPG) policy of the 1990s ushered in a new phase of expansion and massification in Indian higher education. The number of universities, private institutions, and affiliated management colleges increased significantly to cater to the growing demand for management graduates. This expansion was also accompanied by a considerable increase in enrolments for doctoral programs in management and allied disciplines (Borthakur et al., 2024; Jandhyala, 2014; Agarwal, 2009). During this phase, management research in India began to assume larger institutional importance. Doctoral studies created a growing pipeline of early-career scholars, and recruitment and promotion policies of faculty members increasingly incorporated research output as a formal criterion. Gradually, academic careers shifted from a predominantly teaching-led system toward one that placed more importance on publications. As expected, this transition was uneven across institutions. Many newly established M-schools lacked the necessary research infrastructure, mentoring capacity, and intellectual traditions. This has caused wide variation in research quality and outcomes (Khatri et al., 2012).

Although research activity expanded significantly, evaluation frameworks based on global metrics were not yet fully ingrained. The focus was often on increasing the number of publications rather than on meeting stringent quality benchmarks (Mathews et al., 2024). For many scholars, more particularly those in non-elite M-schools, research activities were driven more by institutional growth aspirations and compliance expectations than by coherent, long-term scholarly agendas. However, this phase laid the foundation for later structural imbalance between substantive intellectual contribution and publication volume.

2.3 Global Integration Phase (2005-2015): Internationalisation and Journal Orientation

The early 21st century marked a period of deeper integration of Indian management research into global academic networks. Increased access to foreign journals through digital databases, greater participation in conferences worldwide, and the rise of international research collaborations enabled Indian scholars to dominant global research norms and practices (Hazelkorn, 2015; Moed, 2017; Zou & Ping, 2023). English became the key language of scholarly communication, and this further aligned Indian research with global academic standards.

During this phase, Indian scholars increasingly sought publication in globally indexed journals. Furthermore, Western research paradigms, methodologies, and theoretical frameworks became dominant. Quantitative methods, hypothesis testing, and theory-driven empirical designs gained importance, particularly in areas of strategy, finance, organisational behaviour, etc (Alversson & Sandberg, 2013). Although this paradigm shift significantly improved methodological rigor and comparability, it also raised apprehensions about intellectual dependence and contextual disconnection.

Many scholars have felt that the pressure to publish internationally encouraged “theory borrowing” rather than building indigenous theory. Research issues/questions were often framed to resonate with Western journal audiences, sometimes at the cost of addressing local organisational realities (Mathews et al., 2024). Consequently, although globally visible research output increased, questions persisted about its relevance to Indian scenarios and its contributions to indigenous management thought.

2.4 Contemporary Phase (2015–Present): Metrics, Rankings, and Regulation

The pervasive influence of metrics, rankings, and regulatory oversight on management research in India characterises the most recent phase. International indexing systems such as Scopus, along with curated journal lists such as ABS and ABDC, have become de facto benchmarks for evaluating research quality and impact (Mingers & Willmott, 2012; Serenko & Bontis, 2024). Originally developed for specific national contexts, these lists are now widely used in India to guide publishing strategies and evaluation decisions.

National higher education regulatory bodies have institutionalised these metrics through formal policies. Furthermore, the University Grants Commission (UGC), through mechanisms such as the UGC-CARE list (now, defunct), has linked publications in approved journals to faculty recruitment, promotion, doctoral supervision eligibility, and institutional accreditation (Madhan et al., 2018). The National Institutional Ranking Framework (NIRF) has further intensified this pressure by including research and professional practice indicators into institutional rankings (Mondal & Mondal, 2024). Accordingly, publication counts and journal impact measures are now directly tied to the continuation of services of individuals in the institutions, individual career progression and institutional prestige (Wright & Sharma, 2013).

Although these mechanisms have contributed to a substantial increase in research output, they have also heightened concerns about metric-driven behaviour. Strategic journal targeting, fragmented publications, methodological convergence, and ethical challenges have become increasingly visible (Hicks et al., 2015; Tourish, 2020; Madhan et al., 2018). The coexistence of domestic regulatory controls and global ranking systems has created a complex incentive environment, often marked by conflicting expectations. This confluence of metrics, rankings, and regulation has brought the quantity-quality dilemma into sharp focus, making it a defining feature of contemporary management research in India.

3. CONCEPTUALISING “QUANTITY” AND “QUALITY” IN MANAGEMENT RESEARCH

The discussion on quantity versus quality in management research is basically a debate on how scholarly contribution is defined, measured, and rewarded. Although both dimensions are central to academic systems, their meanings, in practice, are often oversimplified or conflated. In this backdrop, this section analyses and clarifies the concepts of research quantity and research quality, examines competing perspectives on quality, highlighting the limitations of treating the two as binary opposites. Furthermore, particular attention is given to the contextual challenges faced by emerging economies like India.

3.1 Research Quantity

Research quantity denotes the measurable volume of scholarly output produced by an individual, institution, or academic system. The most common indicators include publication counts, frequency of publication, and the number of outputs indexed in major databases such as Scopus or Web of Science (Moed, 2017; Verma & Sharma, 2024). These indicators are widely used as they are relatively easy to quantify, compare, and aggregate across disciplines and institutions (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Indicators of Research Quantity

In addition to simple counts, quantity metrics often assess sustained productivity over time (Rawat & Meena, 2014). Performance of faculty members may be assessed based on publications per year or cumulative publication totals. At the institutional level, research quantity is embedded in accreditation frameworks, funding allocation models, and ranking systems. Universities and M-schools are frequently assessed and accredited/ranked based on aggregate publication output, with varying weights assigned to indexed journals or ranked outlets (Hicks et al., 2015).

These measures play a key role in recruitment, promotion, tenure, and performance appraisal decisions. Therefore, the number of publications has become an overriding indicator of academic productivity on the one hand, and a defining feature of the “publish-or-perish” culture in contemporary academia on the other (Smith et al., 2024). While quantity-based metrics can incentivise research activity and signal minimum scholarly engagement, they constrain substantive contribution or intellectual impact of research (Verma & Sharma, 2024). Publication counts do not clearly distinguish between incremental and significant contributions, nor do they capture the effort and time required for long-term, theory-building work (Mingers & Willmott, 2012). Therefore, quantity indicators are best understood as proxies for activity instead of as measures of scholarly value in themselves.

3.2 Competing Perspectives of Research Quality

In contrast to research quantity, research quality is both a multidimensional and contested concept. In the management literature, quality is commonly associated with rigor, originality, relevance, and impact. From a traditional academic perspective, research quality is frequently operationalised through peer recognition. This recognition is typically measured by publication in high-prestige journals and citation counts (Moed, 2017). The underlying assumption is that rigorous peer review and subsequent citation uptake signify intellectual merit. However, experts have also questioned the adequacy of journal prestige and citations as comprehensive indicators of quality. In their view, such measures are influenced by cumulative advantage, disciplinary conventions, and network effects, which can bias assessments of scholarly contribution (Bornmann, 2017).

Therefore, an alternative perspective places greater emphasis on practitioner and societal impact. From this perspective, management research should address real-world organisational issues/problems, help in policy decisions, and contribute to societal well-being (Bartunek & Rynes, 2014). This perspective emphasises issues between academic impact and practical relevance (Dale et al., 2024). While peers may value theoretical relevance and contribution, practitioners often prioritise actionable insights. The emergence of altmetrics reflects attempts to capture broader societal influence beyond traditional citation-based measures (Kocyigit & Akyol, 2021). Despite these discussions, peer review remains a key mechanism for safeguarding scientific rigor and ethical standards in scholarly work (Chiriboga, 2019).

3.3 Limitations of Binary Framing

The binary framing implies that an increase in quantity necessarily comes at the cost of quality. However, such an assumption is normatively problematic and analytically misleading. High research productivity does not necessarily imply low quality, just as selective publication does not assure intellectual significance (Thomas et al., 2024).

Binary framing supports reductionist evaluation practices that prefer easily measurable indicators over informed judgment. These practices risk rewarding compliance with metric thresholds rather than genuine, valuable/scholarly contributions. Scholars may focus on producing a steady stream of minimally publishable outputs, fragment research projects, and avoid intellectually risky or interdisciplinary work that may yield fewer short-term publications (Tourish, 2020). It is felt by some sections of academics that such environments encourage researchers to prioritise rapid publication over the development of sustained and meaningful research agendas (Alvesson & Jorgen, 2013).

Binary approaches also obscure the temporal dimension of research quality. Many valuable/influential research papers emerge over comparatively long periods, and they may not result in immediate citations or high publication counts. Evaluation systems that

highlight short-term output, therefore, risk undervaluing cumulative, integrative, and foundational research efforts. A more productive perspective recognises that quantity may be a necessary condition for quality but is rarely sufficient on its own.

3.4 Contextual Dimensions of Quality in Emerging Economies

The conceptualisation of research quality is more complex in emerging economies, where higher education institutions (HEIs) are functioning under uneven institutional capacity, resource constraints, and strong regulatory oversight. In such environments, scholars often under dilemma between publishing locally relevant research and achieving global visibility through publication in internationally ranked journals (Mathews et al., 2024).

Globally leading journals tend to privilege theories, methods, and research issues/ questions rooted in Western contexts. This can restrict opportunities for indigenous perspectives and context-sensitive inquiry. Therefore, research addressing local managerial practices, socio-economic challenges, or policy issues may struggle for recognition within mainstream evaluation frameworks, despite its potential relevance and impact (Aguinis & Ramani, 2018). However, when global visibility metrics dominate assessment, quality risks are equated with conformity to external standards rather than with intellectual contributions grounded in local realities (Curry & Lillis, 2014).

For emerging economies like India, fostering a balanced conception of research quality requires recognising contextual scholarship as a legitimate and valuable form of contribution. Indigenous knowledge systems (IKS), problem-oriented research, and region-specific organisational practices provide significant opportunities for theory development and societal impact (Nishant Chakravorty et al., 2022). Integrating these dimensions into evaluation frameworks is necessary for developing a more inclusive research ecosystem that supports both local intellectual autonomy and global engagement.

4. THEORETICAL LENSES FOR ANALYSING RESEARCH EVALUATION

Understanding the quantity-quality dilemma in management research necessitates moving beyond superficial critiques of metrics. It is necessary to examine the deeper theoretical mechanisms that drive and shape research evaluation systems and scholarly behaviour. This section draws on four complementary theoretical lenses, viz., institutional theory, principal-agent theory, academic capitalism, and knowledge production systems (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Theoretical Lenses for Analysing Research Evaluation

These perspectives collectively explain how research evaluation regimes emerge, diffuse, and persist, and how they influence academic conduct in India within a global context.

4.1 Institutional Theory

Institutional theory provides a powerful lens for understanding how research evaluation practices converge across nations and institutions. Organisations adopt structures and practices that are perceived as legitimate within their environment, often leading to institutional isomorphism, where organisations become increasingly similar over time (Powell, 2016; Vukasovic, 2014). In the context of higher education, journal rankings, citation metrics, and indexed publication requirements serve as institutionalised signals of academic credibility. Nonetheless isomorphic pressures operate through three primary mechanisms (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Forms of Institutional Isomorphism

“Coercive isomorphism” arises from formal and informal pressures exerted by regulatory bodies and accreditation agencies. From the perspective of India, organisations such as the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC), UGC, All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE), etc., impose publication-related requirements through recruitment norms, promotion criteria, accreditation frameworks, and funding allocations (Madhan et al., 2018; Mondal & Mondal, 2024). These mandates coerce/compel institutions to prioritise quantitative publication metrics to maintain legitimacy and access critical resources.

“Mimetic isomorphism” arises under conditions of uncertainty. Institutions imitate the practices of globally reputed universities and M-schools that are perceived as successful or prestigious (Powell, 2016; Haapamäki, 2022). Indian HEIs, including M-schools, frequently emulate evaluation criteria and journal preferences associated with international ranking systems such as Scopus, ABDC, and ABS (Serenko & Bontis, 2024). This imitation is influenced by aspirations for reputational enhancement and global visibility (Zafar, 2024).

“Normative isomorphism” arises from professionalisation within academic communities. Professional networks, shared training, and disciplinary norms reinforce common expectations about what constitutes legitimate scholarly behaviour (Haapamäki, 2022). The internalisation of the “publish-or-perish” culture exemplifies this process, as academics view frequent publication as a professional obligation and indicator of competence (Smith et al., 2024).

Notably, global university rankings have intensified these isomorphic pressures. Institutions align their internal performance metrics with those used by these global assessment and accreditation/ranking agencies, often prioritising research output indicators over other dimensions of academic excellence (Zafar, 2024; Mukhlisakhon, 2025). This pursuit of legitimacy through conformity may result in a decoupling between formal policies and substantive research quality, where compliance takes precedence over intellectual contribution (Luden et al., 2025).

4.2 Principal–Agent Theory

Principal–agent theory complements institutional theory/analysis by emphasising incentive structures and behavioural responses within research evaluation systems. In academia, regulatory bodies and university administrations serve as principals, while individual scholars and research units function as agents (Baker, G. P et al., 1988). Principals delegate the task of knowledge production but face information asymmetry, as they cannot directly observe research effort or quality (Elsenhart, 1989). To reduce this asymmetry, principals depend on observable outputs, such as the number of publications, journal rankings, and citation indicators. However, this type of output-based monitoring system creates scope for moral hazard and strategic behaviour (Milgrom & Paul, 1991; Meho, 2025). This may result in agents rationally optimising their actions to satisfy evaluation criteria rather than maximising genuine scholarly contribution.

This misalignment manifests in several forms of gaming behaviour. These include citation manipulation through self-citation or reciprocal citation practices (Meho, 2025), salami slicing of research into multiple publications (Rawat & Meena, 2014), strategic submission to journals with higher acceptance probabilities, predatory publishing (Mertkan et al., 2021), and opportunistic co-authorship (Verma & Sharma, 2024) (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Opportunistic Scholarly Behaviours under Metric-Based Evaluation

These behaviours reflect an incentive structure that rewards compliance with metrics rather than research substance (Chaojin, 2025). Under this intense publish-or-perish pressure, scholars may accord priority for short-term output to secure employment, promotion, and recognition (Smith et al., 2024). This often comes at the cost of long-term research programs, interdisciplinary inquiry, and theory-building efforts (Rawat & Meena, 2014). Principal-agent theory thus emphasises how metric-centric evaluation systems can unintentionally undermine their stated objective of promoting high-quality research.

4.3 Academic Capitalism and the Publish-or-Perish Logic

The concept of academic capitalism situates research evaluation within broader politico-economic transformations of higher education. Academic capitalism represents the increase in market orientation of universities and scholars, driven by competition for funding, status, and talent (Slaughter & Rhoades, 2009). In this environment, scholarly publications serve as both intellectual outputs and forms of academic capital.

The commercialisation of academic publishing plays a crucial role in reinforcing the publish-or-perish culture. Large publishing houses operate on commercial/business principles, while the global expansion of research output has created demand for new journals and rapid publication outlets (Poutoglidou et al., 2022). Journal rankings and impact factors have become key currencies in academic labor markets, influencing hiring, promotion, and funding decisions (Mingers & Willmott, 2012). In this context, several forces intensify publication pressure (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Structural Drivers of Publication Pressure in Academia

Career advancement/progression depends heavily on publication records (Wright & Sharma, 2013). Institutional reputation and rankings rely on faculty research output (Chiriboga, 2019). Research funding is often contingent on demonstrable publication performance (Omoji et al., 2023). Collectively, these factors, among others, create sustained pressure to publish frequently, sometimes at the cost of originality and depth (Elbanna & Child, 2023).

This environment has contributed to the growth of predatory/paid journals, which offer rapid publication without rigorous peer review (Mertkan et al., 2021). It has also diverted scholars' time away from teaching, mentoring, and reflective inquiry. From an academic capitalism perspective, the quantity-quality dilemma indicates structural features of the contemporary knowledge economy rather than isolated individual behaviour.

4.4 Knowledge Production Systems (Mode 1 vs. Mode 2)

The distinction between Mode 1 and Mode 2 knowledge production provides further insight into dilemmas surrounding research evaluation (Michael Gibbons et al., 2010; Levy & Ellis, 2006). Mode 1 knowledge is discipline-based, theory-driven, and produced primarily within academic institutions. It emphasises methodological rigor and peer-controlled quality assurance, typically through

disciplinary journals (Trevorrow & Volmer, 2012). On the other hand, Mode 2 knowledge is problem-oriented, transdisciplinary, and produced in the context of application. It involves collaboration among academics, policymakers, practitioners, and other stakeholders. It prioritises social accountability, relevance, and usefulness (Callan & Rabeharisaa, 2003).

Management research usually spans both modes. Foundational theories are often developed through Mode 1 processes. Additionally, impactful managerial and policy insights require Mode 2 approaches. However, evaluation systems appear to be heavily biased toward Mode 1 outputs. Publications in high-impact academic journals are privileged over policy reports, practitioner-oriented outputs, or collaborative research with demonstrable societal impact.

This bias is particularly challenging in emerging economies such as India, where management research is expected to contribute to development, governance, and institutional capacity-building (Nishant Chakravorty et al., 2022). A rigid reliance on Mode 1 evaluation criteria risks discouraging scholars from engaging in socially relevant, problem-oriented research that addresses local challenges.

4.5 Synthesis of Theoretical Insights

Collectively, these theoretical lenses provide an integrated framework for comprehending research evaluation in Indian management scholarship. Institutional theory signifies the diffusion and persistence of metric-driven evaluation systems through legitimacy-seeking behaviour. Principal-agent theory shows incentive misalignments that encourage strategic compliance and gaming. Academic capitalism emphasises the commercial and competitive forces that intensify publication pressure. Knowledge production theory exposes epistemic biases that privilege disciplinary rigor over societal relevance.

Applied to the Indian context, these perspectives show that the quantity-quality dilemma is a systemic outcome of interacting institutional, economic, and epistemic forces. It is not merely the result of individual scholarly choices. Recognising these dynamics is therefore necessary for developing balanced, context-sensitive research evaluation frameworks, which Section 6 of the paper seeks to advance.

5. EVALUATION REGIMES AND INCENTIVE STRUCTURES IN INDIA

Research evaluation in Indian management scholarship is moulded by a complex interaction of regulatory mandates, institutional performance systems, and domestic and global ranking regimes. These mechanisms were introduced to improve accountability, transparency, and global competitiveness. However, their combined effect has been to reconfigure academic incentives in ways that intensify the quantity-quality dilemma. Against this context, this section examines the architecture of research evaluation in India and analyses how incentive structures influence scholarly behaviour and knowledge production.

5.1 Role of Regulatory Bodies and Accreditation Systems

Regulatory bodies play a pivotal role in defining research expectations within Indian higher education. The UGC sets minimum standards for faculty recruitment, promotion, research grants, and doctoral supervision, with increasing weightage on publication-based criteria (Madhan et al., 2018). The introduction of the UGC-CARE list⁴ was aimed at curbing predatory publishing on the one hand and promoting ethical research practices on the other. It has also reinforced the reliance on indexed journals as primary indicators of research output, creating strong compliance-oriented pressures on institutions and individual scholars. Similarly, the AICTE prescribes research-related criteria for management institutions.

Accreditation agencies such as the NAAC and the National Board of Accreditation (NBA) institutionalise research criteria through structured evaluation frameworks. These frameworks assign weight to publications, citations, funded projects, doctoral output, and other research-related work. Research productivity indicators are particularly influential for institutions seeking higher accreditation grades (Jandhyala, 2014; Agarwal, 2009). National ranking frameworks further amplify these pressures. Parameters such as “Research and Professional Practices” in the NIRF link publication output to institutional legitimacy, visibility, and funding prospects (Mondal & Mondal, 2024).

The above top-down regulatory environment creates strong incentives to increase the number of publications. This is often perceived as a direct pathway to recognition and resource acquisition (Zafar, 2024). In this context, research quality is frequently operationalised through conformity to prescribed publication criteria rather than through substantive peer evaluation.

5.2 Institutional Performance Metrics

At the institutional level, regulatory mandates are translated into internal performance measurement metrics governing recruitment, promotion, tenure, and compensation. Universities and M-schools routinely track the number of publications per faculty member, journal indexing status, and citation counts when making career advancement decisions (Serenko & Bontis, 2024; Wright & Sharma, 2013). Academic Performance Indicator (API) systems and similar scorecards assign numerical values to research outputs, reinforcing the link between publication volume and career advancement (Khatri et al., 2012).

Furthermore, performance-linked incentives, accelerated promotions, and eligibility for doctoral supervision intensify these pressures. Institutions also monitor bibliometric data from databases such as Google Scholar and Scopus, which are often used to

support institutional ranking efforts (Mingers et al., 2017). Consequently, publication counts and annual output rates become highly significant indicators of academic success.

While such systems may increase aggregate research output, they also shape scholarly behaviour in significant ways. Therefore, faculty members are, in a way, forced/pressurised to prioritise indexed publications irrespective of the depth, originality, or relevance of their work. Particularly, early-career scholars face more pressure to demonstrate rapid productivity, often at the cost of developing coherent and sustained research agendas. Teaching quality, mentoring, and engagement with practice or policy communities receive comparatively lower recognition. This again reinforces a publication-centric academic culture featured by mechanical productivity rather than reflective inquiry (Matyo-Cepero & Stathene, 2016).

5.3 Journal Lists, Rankings, and Their Consequences

Journal lists and ranking systems have become key instruments in research evaluation, serving as proxies for quality and legitimacy. Scopus indexing, in particular, has acquired symbolic and practical significance in Indian academia. International lists such as ABDC and ABS are also increasingly referenced, especially by institutions seeking global recognition (Mingers & Willmott, 2012; Serenko & Bontis, 2024).

While these lists provide some degree of quality assurance, their widespread use raises a few concerns. Journal rankings are inherently selective and moulded by disciplinary, regional, and methodological biases. Many high-quality journals focusing on emerging economic issues, public sector management, or interdisciplinary and indigenous perspectives remain underrepresented or excluded (Mathews et al., 2024). This results in disincentives for scholars to pursue research that is locally relevant but misaligned with dominant global outlets (Curry & Lillis, 2014).

Furthermore, the conflation of journal prestige with article quality overlooks variation in contribution within journals. It reinforces cumulative advantage and encourages scholars to prioritise ranked outlets even when research issues are poorly aligned with local contexts or societal needs. Over the years, this has led to the homogenisation of research agendas, increased reliance on Western paradigms, and a narrowing of acceptable methods and topics (Mathews et al., 2024). Journal lists thus function less as neutral quality filters and more as institutionalised signals that mould scholarly behaviour and research priorities.

5.4 Unintended Consequences

The combined effect of regulatory mandates, institutional metrics, and journal rankings has caused several unintended consequences that directly affect research quality and integrity. One widely observed outcome is salami slicing, where a single study is fragmented into multiple minimally publishable outputs to inflate publication counts (Rawat & Meena, 2014). However, although formally compliant with evaluation criteria, such practices dilute intellectual coherence and undermine cumulative knowledge development (Thomas et al., 2024).

Another effect is the persistence of predatory publishing. Intense publication pressure, combined with uneven research capacity and limited mentoring, makes scholars vulnerable to journals that prioritise fees over rigorous peer review (Mertkan et al., 2021; Poutoglidou et al., 2022). Although these outlets are excluded from approved lists, the underlying incentive structure continues to reward quantity-driven performance.

Additionally, methodological imitation may result in a further risk. Scholars may adopt theories and methods not because they best suit and address research questions, but because they are preferred by highly ranked journals (Alvesson & Jorgen, 2013). This discourages innovation, contextual sensitivity, and critical inquiry (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2013). Over the years, the need to produce rapid outputs also discouraged long-term, ambitious, theory-building research projects (Alvesson & Jorgen, 2013).

In addition, publication pressure can result in broader ethical transgressions, including plagiarism, data manipulation, and false authorship (Poutoglidou et al., 2022; Downer et al., 2025). These dynamics erode trust in scholarly outputs and damage the credibility of the academic environment. Collectively, these unintended consequences emphasise the shortcomings of evaluation regimes that rely excessively on quantitative proxies for quality. The analysis brings the point to the fore that there is a need for more nuanced, context-sensitive research assessment frameworks.

6. TOWARDS A BALANCED FRAMEWORK FOR RESEARCH EVALUATION

The above analysis shows that the quantity-quality dilemma in management research is not merely a technical problem of measurement. It is a structural issue rooted in how scholarly work is conceptualised, evaluated, and rewarded. Addressing this dilemma requires going beyond narrow bibliometric indicators towards a context-sensitive and holistic approach to the evaluation of research work. This section makes an attempt to propose a balanced approach/framework that reconceptualises research quality, integrates multiple dimensions of scholarly contribution, and incorporates institutional diversity and career-stage differences. At the same time, it remains compatible with academic standards worldwide.

6.1 Reframing Quality Beyond Metrics

An important limitation of the extant research evaluation regimes is their tendency to equate quality with a narrow set of quantitative indicators, such as the number of research papers published, journal rankings, and citation metrics. Although these metrics provide

administrative convenience and comparability, they capture only a partial and often distorted view of scholarly excellence (Hicks et al., 2015; Verma & Sharma, 2024). Research excellence can be understood with many a number of interrelated dimensions (Figure 8). Anyhow, a balanced evaluation framework requires a multidimensional understanding of research quality.

Figure 8: Multidimensional Dimensions of Research Excellence

- “Rigor” refers to methodological soundness and intellectual thoroughness in research design, data collection, and analysis (Meyer, 2017; Percie et al., 2020).
- “Originality” captures the extent to which research introduces novel ideas, concepts, theories, or approaches that advance the field (Alverson & Sandberg, 2013; Alverson & Jorgen, 2013).
- “Relevance” is about the significance of research issues/questions for academic debates, policy discourse, or managerial practice (Voegtlin et al., 2022).
- “Impact” extends beyond academic influence to include broader societal, economic, and organisational effects (Charnock et al., 2024).
- “Ethical conduct and research integrity” are integral to quality, encompassing transparency, responsible data practices, and adherence to ethical standards across the research process (Kretser et al., 2019; Poutoglidou et al., 2022).
- “Engagement and dissemination” further shape quality by explaining how effectively research reaches and influences diverse audiences beyond academia (Mannay, 2012).

These dimensions do not manifest uniformly across disciplines, research types, or institutional contexts. What constitutes excellence in basic theoretical research may differ from applied or policy-oriented inquiry (Mythili et al., 2025). However, reframing quality beyond metrics does not mean rejecting quantitative indicators altogether. Rather, metrics should serve as supplementary signals that inform, but do not substitute for, informed peer judgment. This approach aligns with principles of responsible research evaluation that emphasise reflexivity, transparency, and contextual interpretation (Wilsdon et al., 2015). For management research in India, such reframing is necessary to counterbalance compliance-driven publication behaviour and to encourage deeper intellectual engagement.

6.2 Proposed Conceptual Framework

Building on this reframing, this paper proposes an integrated conceptual framework for evaluation of research structured around four interconnected dimensions: inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes. This framework shifts focus from narrow output metrics to the full research value chain, recognising that high-quality scholarship emerges from sustained investment and supportive institutional environments (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Input-Process-Output-Outcome Framework for Research Evaluation

“Inputs” refer to the foundational capacities that enable research activity. These include (i) human capital, such as faculty expertise and doctoral training (Dwivedi & Joshi, 2019; Sri Wahyuningsih et al., 2025); (ii) material resources, comprising funding, access to databases, software, and libraries (Omoji et al., 2023; Borthakur et al., 2024); and (iii) institutional support systems, such as mentoring structures, research offices, and ethical review mechanisms (Jandhyala, 2014). Any evaluation system that ignores input

adequacies risk penalising scholars and institutions operating under structural constraints, particularly in emerging academic environments.

“Processes” capture how research is conducted or carried out. This includes the robustness of research design, clarity of research issues/questions, and appropriateness of methods (Meyer, 2017). It also encompasses collaboration across disciplines, institutions, and national boundaries (Castañer & Oliveira, 2020; Compagnucci & Spigarelli, 2020). Ethical conduct and integrity are key/vital process elements, comprising transparency in reporting, responsible authorship, and avoidance of questionable research practices (Kretser et al., 2019; Chiriboga, 2019). Focusing on process quality enables shift evaluation away from purely outcome-based judgments towards practices that sustain long-term research integrity and innovation (Aguinis & Ramani, 2018).

“Outputs” consist of traditional scholarly products such as journal articles, books, book chapters, and monographs (Wright & Sharma, 2013). They also comprise theory-building contributions, conceptual integration, and policy- or practice-oriented outputs that inform decision-making (Voegtlin et al., 2022; Mathews et al., 2024). Evaluation should focus not only on the number of outputs, but also on their intellectual ambition, coherence, and contribution to knowledge development.

“Outcomes” signify the longer-term and broader effects of research. Academic influence includes citations, theoretical uptake, and methodological adoption by other scholars (Gasparyan et al., 2018). Societal impact encompasses contributions to policy change, organisational improvement, and public understanding (Charnock et al., 2024; Elbanna & Child, 2023). Long-term significance recognises that some research yields its greatest value over extended periods, beyond short evaluation cycles. Including outcomes underscores the ultimate purpose of scholarly inquiry beyond immediate productivity.

6.3 Differentiated Expectations Across Institutions and Career Stages

A further shortcoming in the existing evaluation regimes is their reliance on uniform expectations across diverse institutional contexts and career stages. A balanced framework must explicitly recognise heterogeneity in disciplinary norms, institutional missions, and scholarly trajectories (Chandra, 2025).

Research-intensive universities and autonomous M-schools may reasonably prioritise theory development, international publication, and doctoral training. Even in such settings, evaluation should privilege quality, originality, and impact over sheer publication volume. Teaching-oriented institutions, by contrast, may place greater emphasis on applied research, scholarship of teaching and learning, pedagogical innovation, and regional engagement (Jonathan, 2025). Imposing identical publication benchmarks across these contexts risks distorting institutional priorities and undermining mission differentiation (Hazelkorn, 2015).

Differentiation is equally important across career stages. Early-career researchers require space to develop methodological competence, theoretical grounding, and coherent research agendas (Charnock et al., 2024; Kwamie & Jalaghoonia, 2020). At this stage, evaluation should focus on research potential, quality of initial outputs, and engagement in research processes rather than aggressive quantitative targets (Wright & Sharma, 2013). Senior scholars are better positioned to pursue ambitious, integrative, and interdisciplinary projects. They also contribute through mentoring, research leadership, and societal engagement, which may involve fewer but more impactful outputs (Moher et al., 2018). Evaluation frameworks should reflect these evolving roles.

6.4 Integrating Global Standards with Local Relevance

A balanced evaluation framework must reconcile global academic standards with the need for locally relevant and contextually grounded research. Global engagement is necessary for visibility, comparability, and participation in global knowledge networks. However, uncritical adoption of global benchmarks can marginalise research addressing indigenous contexts, institutional specificities, and developmental challenges (Mathews et al., 2024).

Encouraging contextualised and indigenous management research requires explicit recognition of its scholarly value. Research on Indian organisational forms, public sector management, informal economies, and social enterprises should be valued, even when it draws on indigenous theories or employs methods less favoured by mainstream international journals (Mathews et al., 2024). Expanding the range of legitimate publication outlets, including high-quality Indian journals and policy-oriented platforms, can support this objective (Abalkina, 2024).

Evaluation frameworks should also reward transdisciplinary and problem-oriented research that generates Mode 2 knowledge and addresses complex societal challenges (Callan & Rabeharisaa, 2003). Supporting open science practices, including open access publishing and data sharing, can further enhance visibility, transparency, and societal engagement (Nishant Chakravorty et al., 2022; Mckiernan, 2017). By integrating global standards with local relevance, India can foster a research ecosystem that is globally credible, socially responsive, and intellectually autonomous.

7. POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND STRATEGIC RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis made so far shows that the quantity-quality dilemma in management research is embedded within broader governance, incentive, and evaluative structures. Addressing this dilemma calls for coordinated action across multiple levels of the academic system. In this backdrop, this section outlines policy implications and strategic recommendations for regulators and policymakers, institutions and research leaders, and individual scholars, with the primary objective of fostering a more balanced, ethical, and sustainable research ecosystem in India.

7.1 Implications for Regulators and Policymakers

Regulatory and accreditation/ranking bodies such as the UGC, AICTE, NAAC, NBA and NIRF exercise decisive influence over research culture through assessment frameworks, accreditation criteria, and eligibility norms (Madhan et al., 2018). A major implication of this study is the need to redesign research evaluation systems to move beyond narrow output-based metrics towards holistic and context-sensitive approaches. Quantitative indicators can act as reference points. However, they should not function as the sole or dominant basis for assessing research performance (Hicks et al., 2015; Verma & Sharma, 2024; Chandra, 2025).

In this context, it is necessary, on a priority basis, to avoid one-size-fits-all metrics. It may be noted here that the HEIs differ significantly from the perspectives of mission, capacity, disciplinary orientation, etc. Research-intensive universities, teaching-focused colleges, and specialised M-schools require differentiated expectations and evaluation criteria (Chandra, 2025; Mondal & Mondal, 2024). Uniform publication thresholds risk distorting institutional priorities and encouraging superficial compliance rather than meaningful scholarship (Hazelkorn, 2015). Therefore, regulators should allow flexibility in how research contributions are demonstrated, highlighting alignment with institutional mandates rather than mechanical benchmarking.

Strengthening qualitative peer review mechanisms is equally important. Expert panels, narrative research portfolios, and structured self-assessment reports can complement quantitative indicators and provide richer insights into intellectual substance. Such mechanisms reduce incentives for metric gaming and encourage deeper engagement with research quality. Policymakers should also promote research integrity by strengthening policies against plagiarism, predatory publishing, and data manipulation, alongside educational initiatives that reinforce ethical research conduct (Kretser et al., 2019; Poutoglidou et al., 2022).

Finally, regulatory frameworks should explicitly recognise diverse forms of scholarly contribution. Policy-oriented research, practice-relevant studies, indigenous and contextual scholarship, and societal engagement should be valued within formal evaluation systems (Elbanna & Child, 2023). Investment in research infrastructure, including access to databases, software, and professional research support staff, is also crucial to enable quality-oriented research across institutions (Poudel, 2022).

7.2 Implications for Institutions and Research Deans

Institutions and research leaders/deans act as intermediaries between regulatory mandates and individual scholars. Their internal policies translate external expectations into everyday academic practice. A major implication for institutions is the need to shift from a compliance-driven approach to research management towards the cultivation of a genuine research culture. Building such a culture requires prioritising long-term capacity-building over short-term publication targets. Strong mentorship systems are essential, particularly for early-career faculty members navigating complex and often contradictory evaluation environments. Structured mentoring supports the development of coherent research agendas, methodological competence, and ethical awareness, thereby enhancing both productivity and quality over time (Aguinis & Ramani, 2018).

Institutions should invest in capacity-building initiatives, including research methodology workshops, academic writing support, and collaborative research platforms. These initiatives reduce dependence on mechanical output maximisation and enable scholars to pursue ambitious, integrative projects (Westover, 2025; Alvesson & Jorgen, 2013). Ethical standards should be reinforced through transparent review processes and clear guidance on authorship norms, data management, and responsible publication practices.

Institutional performance management systems also require recalibration. Teaching innovation, doctoral supervision, interdisciplinary collaboration, and engagement with industry or policy stakeholders should be recognised alongside publications. By broadening definitions of academic success, institutions can reduce quantity-driven pressure and create an environment that values intellectual depth, relevance, and integrity.

7.3 Implications for Individual Scholars

For individual scholars, particularly in management disciplines, the findings underscore the importance of strategic rather than mechanical approaches to research productivity. Strategic publishing involves aligning research topics, methods, and outlets with long-term scholarly goals, theoretical interests, and ethical commitments, rather than maximising publication counts alone.

Scholars are encouraged to prioritise coherence and depth in their research agendas, even if this results in fewer publications in the short term. Engaging in theory-building, interdisciplinary inquiry, and context-sensitive research involves higher intellectual risk. However, it also provides greater potential for sustained scholarly impact and relevance (Bartunek & Rynes, 2014). Balancing rigor, relevance, and responsibility requires conscious reflection on the purposes of research and the audiences it intends to serve.

Simultaneously, scholars must navigate existing evaluation systems pragmatically. Awareness of journal expectations, transparent methodological reporting, and collaborative research networks can improve publication prospects without compromising intellectual integrity. Senior scholars also carry a responsibility to mentor junior colleagues and model ethical, quality-oriented research behaviour. Through reflective and principled engagement, individual scholars can contribute to reshaping academic norms from within.

Collectively, these recommendations emphasise that resolving the quantity-quality dilemma is a shared responsibility. Sustainable reform requires alignment across institutional leadership, individual scholarly practice, and policy frameworks, grounded in a common commitment to meaningful and responsible knowledge production.

8. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This final section consolidates the key arguments of the paper and reflects on their broader implications for management research evaluation in India. It summarises the theoretical insights developed, highlights the contributions of the paper to scholarship and practice, and acknowledges key limitations. The section concludes by outlining directions for future research that can empirically extend and refine the proposed framework.

8.1 Summary of Key Arguments

This study has examined the persistent and increasingly salient dilemma between research quantity and research quality in the evolution of management research in India. Situated within the broader transformation of higher education and global academic governance, the analysis illustrates that the quantity-quality dilemma is not merely a matter of individual scholarly choice. Rather, it is a systemic outcome shaped by regulatory mandates, institutional incentive structures, and international evaluation regimes.

By tracing the phased evolution of management research in India, the paper shows how metric-driven assessment practices have progressively redefined academic priorities and research behaviour. Publication counts, journal rankings, and citation indicators have become dominant indicators of scholarly value. While these metrics address concerns related to productivity, accountability, and visibility, they have also resulted in unintended consequences, including publication inflation, ethical vulnerabilities, methodological conformity, and reduced attention to long-term theory-building.

Drawing on institutional theory, principal-agent theory, academic capitalism, and knowledge production systems, the study explains how global norms and local governance structures interact to sustain metric-centric evaluation cultures. Notably, it challenges the binary framing of quantity versus quality. It argues that these are distinct but interrelated dimensions of scholarly activity that require balanced and context-sensitive evaluation rather than hierarchical substitution.

8.2 Theoretical and Practical Contributions

The paper makes a few theoretical contributions to the literature on research evaluation and academic governance. First, it advances understanding of metric-centric evaluation regimes by integrating multiple theoretical lenses into a coherent analytical framework. This synthesis provides deeper insight into why quantitative assessment systems persist, despite widespread recognition of their limitations, particularly in emerging academic systems.

Second, the paper reconceptualises research quality as a multidimensional construct encompassing rigor, originality, relevance, and impact. By moving beyond narrow bibliometric proxies, it contributes to ongoing debates on responsible research evaluation and challenges reductionist interpretations of scholarly excellence.

From a practical perspective, the study proposes a balanced and actionable framework for research evaluation structured around inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes. This framework provides an alternative to output-dominated assessment models and provides guidance for regulators, institutions, and scholars seeking to align productivity with meaningful scholarly contribution. By explicitly incorporating institutional diversity and career-stage differentiation, the paper also contributes to policy discussions on fairness, effectiveness, and sustainability in academic performance management.

8.3 Limitations of the Study

This study is subject to limitations inherent in conceptual and theory-driven research. It does not draw on primary empirical data or systematic bibliometric analysis. As a result, it cannot assess the magnitude, variation, or distribution of quantity-quality dilemmas across institutions, sub-disciplines, or regions. While the arguments are grounded in established theory and prior scholarship, the proposed framework requires empirical validation.

In addition, the focus on management research in India, while analytically instructive, limits direct generalisation to other disciplines or national contexts. Differences in epistemic traditions, regulatory environments, and institutional capacity may require contextual adaptation of the framework.

8.4 Directions for Future Research

Future research can extend this study in a few directions. First, empirical testing of the proposed evaluation framework is a critical next step. Mixed-methods studies combining bibliometric analysis, surveys, and qualitative interviews could examine how inputs, processes, outputs, and outcomes interact in practice and how they relate to perceptions of research quality and impact.

Second, comparative studies across management sub-disciplines could explore whether the quantity-quality dilemma manifests differently in fields with distinct methodological and theoretical orientations. Cross-national comparative research would further illuminate how evaluation regimes operate across emerging and advanced academic systems.

Finally, longitudinal studies tracking changes in research behaviour over time could provide valuable insights into the long-term consequences of metric-driven evaluation and the conditions under which balanced assessment frameworks support sustainable and socially relevant knowledge production.

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